

CS - MACH1

Deliverable D6.4: Project Website

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November 2025

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project funded by the European Union (GA 101214613). Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document details	
Project Acronym / Name	CS-MACH1
Project URL	www.cs-mach1.eu
Project Type	HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
EU Call	HORIZON-MISS-2024-OCEAN-01
Grant Agreement No.	Project 101214613
Project Start Date	1 June 2025
Project end date	30 November 2027
Work Package	WP6- Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
Deliverable	D6.4- Main project website online and running
Due date of Deliverable	November 2025
Actual Submission date	
Lead Beneficiary for this deliverable	OutBe
Reviewed by	
Revision	
Dissemination level	Public
Number of pages	23

Document history			
Version	Date	Comment	Modification made by
1.0	08/10/2025	First Draft	Arianna Liconti
2.0	09/10/2025	Minor edits	Joseph Nolan, Camilla Campanati, Antonio Novellino
3.0	10/11/2025	Minor edits	Arianna Liconti

To cite this document:

Liconti A., Vuolo N. & Giroto F. (2025). D6.2: CS-MACH1 Project Website. Deliverable of the Horizon Europe project CS-MACH1 (Grant Agreement No. 101214613).

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List of referenced acronyms

CMCC	Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change
CS	Citizen Science
CS-MACH1	MArine Citizen science data Horizon
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
EDITO	European Digital Twin Ocean
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EurOBIS	European node of the Ocean Biodiversity Information System
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTTP/SSL	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure / Secure Sockets Layer
MCS	Marine Citizen Science
MCSDN	Marine Citizen Science Data Network
MCSI	Marine Citizen Science Initiatives
OBPS	Ocean Best Practices System
OutBe	OutBe S.R.L.
SCOOP	Solutions for Cost-effective Ocean Observation Platform
SeaDataNet	Pan-European infrastructure for ocean & marine data management
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SMHI	Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute
SSBE	Seascape Belgium
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

A project website [cs-mach1.eu] has been developed for CS-MACH1 to allow wide communication and outreach of the project.

The development process was led by OutBe in collaboration with all consortium partners, whose input and feedback were invaluable in determining the repository structure, wireframe and content.

The **CS-MACH1 project website** serves as the central digital hub, hosting a summary of information and resources about the project and pages to accommodate all the main parts and results of the project as it progresses, for example CS-MACH1 resources, guidelines, secretariat members, data platforms and pilot projects call to action and results.

2. Introduction

The **CS-MACH1 project website** is the digital gateway to the *Marine Citizen Science Data Network (MCSDN)*. It functions as both a communication hub and a **web directory** connecting marine citizen science initiatives (MCSI), data-management experts, cost-efficient technology developers, and scientists across Europe.

As leaders of CS-MACH1 T6.2, OutBe built the Website in-house utilising the Digital team expertise. The aims of the website were to:

- Provide a **central resource hub** hosting all the project outputs, including deliverables, publications, training materials, guidelines, protocols, and communication assets;
- Reach out to and **engage a broad range of CS stakeholders**;
- Enable **discoverability and accessibility** of best practices, FAIR-data workflows, cost-efficient technologies, and marine citizen-science projects.
- Serve as the **entry point for the MCSDN**, linking to partner infrastructures such as **EU-Citizen.Science, EMODnet, SeaDataNet, EurOBIS, OBPS, SCOOP, and CoastPredict**.
- Support **open-science practices** by ensuring all outputs, materials, and deliverables are freely accessible online and archived.
- Ensure **long-term sustainability** beyond the project.

A development process was followed (see section 3) to deliver the initial site design and content (see section 4).

3. Development Process

After studying internally with the OutBe digital team the potential structure of the website based on the project proposal, an initial workshop was held in person during the Kick-Off Meeting, with all CS-MACH1 partners, presenting an initial proposal layout and discussing together the requirements for website development, functionalities and content. Following the consortium in-person workshop, OutBe team took these inputs internally to redefine the project website initial layout with the received feedback. A wireframe was then finalised in partnership with SSBE and CMCC, respectively leader of WP6 and

project coordinator of CS-MACH1. The whole development process of the website ran at the same time of the development of the project visual identity, always carried out by OutBe, in order to arrive at the final decision of the project website structure with a defined visual identity and logo to base the graphic design of the website on. The final wireframe of the project website - developed on the collaborative platform [figma.com](https://www.figma.com) - alongside the visual identity and brand guidelines was presented in September 2025 (M4) during an online WP6 meeting.

3.1 Domain & Technical Specifications

The CS-MACH1 project website was developed and hosted under the domain www.cs-mach1.eu, created to ensure coherence, visibility, and long-term recognition within the European research and innovation landscape. The *.eu* domain reflects the project's pan-European scope and maternity, and its alignment with Horizon Europe and Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters" objectives. The structure "cs-mach1" directly conveys the project identity – *Citizen Science (CS)* combined with *Mach1*, a metaphor for speed, innovation, and acceleration towards data integration and impact. The website is designed and hosted using [FRAMER](#), an intuitive and secure web design platform that allows for collaborative development, adaptive layouts, and efficient content management. FRAMER was selected for its ability to integrate dynamic, visually engaging components (e.g., interactive directories and data visualisations) while maintaining accessibility and sustainability standards required by EU projects. Core features include integrated security protocols (HTTPS/SSL certification), cross-device compatibility, and compliance with **WCAG 2.1 accessibility standards**. This setup ensures that the CS-MACH1 website remains both technically robust and easily maintainable by OutBe's team during and beyond the project's lifetime. Built-in **search-engine optimisation (SEO)** supports discoverability through relevant keywords, meta-descriptions, and structured data tags to maximise visibility on European and international search engines.

3.2 Site Map

The structure of the CS-MACH1 main website was designed to ensure clarity, accessibility, and user engagement while reflecting the project's multidimensional nature. The structure follows a logical and intuitive hierarchy that mirrors the main pillars of CS-MACH1 – *networking, capacity building, data integration, and communication*. By adopting a modular architecture,

each section functions independently yet remains interconnected through a consistent navigation flow, allowing users to move seamlessly between project information, training resources, and data tools. This approach enhances both usability and scalability, enabling the platform to evolve as the network grows. The design also supports different user profiles – from citizen-science practitioners to data managers and policymakers – ensuring that each can quickly locate relevant content without overwhelming complexity. Overall, the wireframe reflects the project’s emphasis on openness, interoperability, and long-term sustainability, translating its conceptual framework into a coherent digital experience. Previous EU project websites that include citizen science elements (see <https://walnutproject.eu/>, <https://mrv4soc.eu/>, <https://guardians-project.eu/>) and associated projects (see <https://missionoceanwaters.eu/#/>, <https://www.scoop-ocean.org>, <https://digitaltwinocan.mercator-ocean.eu/>) have been consulted to inform the final design, shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Wireframe of CS-MACH1 Project Website pages

3.3 Content

Following the initial development process, the wireframe of the project website was designed with the following **core sections**.

Table 1. Core sections of CS-MACH1 Project Website wireframe

Section	Description
Home	Overview of CS-MACH1 mission, partners, main pages (Network, Training, Pilots) and latest news;
About	Presentation of the project vision, objectives, structure and consortium;
Network	MCSDN description ready to collect the addition to the network of technology developers, data-management experts, and marine researchers, managed by the Secretariat. Includes join up email for potential members;
Training & Resources	Access to e-learning modules, video tutorials, best-practice documents, and protocols for FAIR data, cost-efficient devices, and metadata management. Includes search and filter functions (type of resource, theme);
Explore Data	Overview of how CS data can feed into EU infrastructures (EMODnet, EurOBIS, SeaDataNet). Will include guidance for dataset submission, quality control, and attribution;
Pilot Projects	Presentation of the demonstration use-cases (in Northern and Southern Europe Seas) with future links to call to actions, initiatives trialled, results, best practices and visual dashboards;
News & Events	Press releases, updates, call to action, publications, workshop and conference participation and organisation (e.g., ECSA 2026).
Deliverables	Repository of public deliverables, scientific articles, policy briefs, and open-access materials;
Impact	The Impact page highlights CS-MACH1's policy outputs, sustainability roadmap, and data applications within EDITO and CoastPredict .
Contact	Contact form, social-media links, and singular institution contacts.

The descriptive content of the CS-MACH1 website, outlining the project’s aims and objectives, has been largely derived from the **Description of Action (DoA), Annex 1 of the EC Grant Agreement**, and subsequently adapted and edited to ensure it is accessible and engaging for a wide audience beyond the scientific community. The website presents the project’s mission, structure, and outputs in clear, public-friendly language while maintaining consistency with the Horizon Europe framework and Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters” objectives.

All **CS-MACH1 deliverables and publications** are and will remain available for download as part of the project’s open-science approach. Dedicated pages host these outputs, ensuring transparency and long-term accessibility through external repositories such as **Zenodo** and direct links to related infrastructures (e.g., EMODnet, OBPS).

Links to all official project **social-media channels** (LinkedIn, Instagram, Youtube) are integrated in the footer, which appears on every page of the site. These will be regularly updated in alignment with Task 6.3 (*Communication Materials: Visual Identity and Social Media*), ensuring coherent messaging and visibility across platforms.

All imagery used on the website is either covered by the appropriate **Creative Commons licence** or reproduced with the permission of the copyright holder, particularly regarding consortium logos, partner and advisory board photographs, and other branded visual assets.

The **Data Protection and Privacy Policy**, accessible through the footer, has been developed in compliance with **EU GDPR (2016/679)** and relevant national regulations. It will be reviewed and updated throughout the duration of the project to ensure full adherence to data-protection standards.

Acknowledgement of the **EU funding** supporting CS-MACH1 is displayed on every page footer in accordance with the Horizon Europe visibility guidelines, including the EU emblem, disclaimer, and references to the Grant Agreement.

As the project evolves, the CS-MACH1 website will progressively integrate new content aligned with the project’s work plan and deliverables.

4. Website Content

The CS-MACH1 website serves as a **comprehensive gateway to the project's activities and outputs**. It brings together all key sections — from background information and training resources to data tools, pilot projects, and the network directory — providing users with a clear overview of how the project connects and strengthens marine citizen science across Europe. Designed as both an information hub, a functional re-directory and a collaboration space, the website reflects the project's open-science approach and its ambition to strengthen marine citizen science across Europe. It enables users to explore how citizen-generated data can support EU data infrastructures such as EMODnet, SeaDataNet, and EurOBIS, while also accessing best-practice materials, FAIR-data guidelines, and learning modules to improve data quality and interoperability. The website provides a unified platform for scientists, policymakers, technology developers, and citizens to connect, share, and contribute to a more inclusive and coordinated marine observation community.

4.1 Website Header & Footer

The header and footer of the CS-MACH1 website (*Figure 2*) appear on every page, giving the user an **easy way to navigate to the other main locations of the site at any time**, while also knowing the project main timeline, social media links and maternity. The terms used in the menu were chosen for simplicity and accessibility from a variety of different audience types, following the multidisciplinary nature of the project.

Figure 2. Header and footer of CS-MACH1 Project Website.

4.2 Home Page

The Home page serves as the main entry point to the CS-MACH1 website and provides an immediate overview of the project’s purpose, identity, and scope. It introduces visitors to the mission of CS-MACH1 – to accelerate the integration and recognition of marine citizen-science data across Europe – and highlights how the project contributes to the broader goals of Horizon Europe and the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters.” The first project animation (*Figure 3*) brings the logo to life, emphasising the dynamicity of the project, and graphically explaining

how the project brings all the diverse protagonists of marine citizen science together, always placing people and data at the center.

Figure 3. Stills of CS-MACH1 Project Website Home page.

The page presents a concise summary of the project’s objectives, structure, and partnership, offering a visual gateway to the main sections of the site such as the Network, Training & Resources, and Project’s Pilots . A **project overview infographic** based on the one present in the project proposal, was custom made for the page and communication materials, showing CS-MACH1 main elements (*Figure 4*). Dynamic elements including news updates, featured stories, and calls to action ensure that the homepage remains current and engaging throughout the project’s lifespan. The design emphasises clarity, inclusivity, and accessibility, using simple navigation and key visuals to reflect the collaborative and data-driven nature of the initiative. As a whole, the Home page encapsulates CS-MACH1’s ambition to connect people, knowledge, and technology in pursuit of a smarter and more sustainable ocean observation system.

Figure 4. Project overview custom made infographic present in CS-MACH1 website Home page.

4.3 About page

The About page provides visitors with a **clear understanding of the CS-MACH1 project** – its origins, objectives, structure, consortium partners, and project’s positioning within the wider European research and innovation landscape. It explains how the project builds on the need to strengthen marine citizen science as a credible and integral component of ocean observation, helping to bridge the gap between MCSIs, scientists, and policymakers. The page outlines the project’s main goals: to create a MCSDN, to harmonise data standards and protocols, and to improve the FAIRness and usability of citizen-generated data. It also introduces the consortium partners and their complementary expertise, showing how each contributes to data management, technology development, communication, and engagement. The page is designed to convey both the scientific excellence and the collaborative spirit of the project, situating CS-MACH1 as a central actor in advancing open, trusted, and inclusive marine citizen science in Europe (Figure 5).

CS-MACH1 is creating a network for citizen science initiatives, cost-efficient technology providers, data management experts, and training material to facilitate FAIR data flows, empowering citizens to monitor and contribute to marine science through data platforms. It is not another webpage, but a directory built on top of existing infrastructures.

SO 4
Maximize the data uptake and impact

Maximize the data uptake through development of dedicated training materials and toolkits, preparing the CS initiatives for projects, supporting the data integration and uptake together with additional and other such as the stakeholder community and in line with the EU data infrastructure requirements.

SO 5
Demonstrate the full potential of CS observation data

Implement new mode demonstrators of the proposed framework in two different use cases, using cost-efficient devices, marine CS concepts, and demonstrate the resulting platform value to several data providers.

SO 6
Communicate the developed citizen science data approach

Strengthen the network and empower the different communities involved, communicating the latest MACH1 developments and other results of the project to involve the wider audience, as well as create a clear personal accountability plan for the community.

AIM

Building a Marine Citizen Science Data Network to empower citizens to share their data and facilitate data uptake and integration by end users

HOW

Support operational integration to the whole citizen science data network and provide the necessary technology and data management training to support field data flows

IMPACT

Maximize the full potential of Marine Citizen Science by engaging citizens and transforming collected data into accessible, practical knowledge for wider academic and scientific impact

WORK PACKAGES

- WP1 Project coordination and management
- WP2 Connecting the dots: Set up of the Marine Citizen Science Data Network
 - Task 2.1 Mapping of the data information of MCS initiatives and communities (M1 - M12)
 - Task 2.2 Identification of the appropriate platform to share data information of CS initiatives and communities (M6 - M16)
 - Task 2.3 Activation and management of the Marine Citizen Science Data Network (M1 - M32)
- WP3 Harmonising marine citizen science data collection and management
- WP4 Magnifying the impact of marine citizen science
- WP5 Work package 5: Demonstrating the value chain of Marine Citizen Science Data Network
- WP6 Communication, dissemination and exploitation

FAIR data definition for CSMACH1

Findable

CS-MACH1 will propose methods to make citizen science data Findable in EU aggregation through operational pipelines where possible. Cost-efficient servers and their data storage will be always a human indexing and handling of data. Online metadata, such as those from local sources, will be reported in EMDirect Data together with metadata related to a DOI for referencing.

Accessible

Accessibility of the CS data is key for uptake and acceptance of data by potential users. Data sets made available following the above described process, via international agreements or more easily accessible.

Interoperable

Achieving interoperability between different data sources requires using common standards and domain vocabularies to describe attributes like parameters, units, and precision types. Device marine data needs to be compatible with EMDirect. CS-MACH1 will analyse existing datasets, metadata, and services to recommend best practices for generating metadata aligned with standards.

Reusable

Metadata should include information about the quality and origin of the dataset to ensure its reusability. For cost-efficient servers, referencing the sensor-ID in a unique DOI/URL/ID allows users to access data quality. This helps ensure metadata about data reusability. For other data, such as locally hosted datasets, components, details on the protocols followed, and the user's expertise are crucial for ensuring data reusability.

Acknowledgement

This project aims to establish best practices for implementing the FAIR principles also on availability and promotion for CS data, an area that is not yet well defined. A key focus is on acknowledging contributions, particularly critical in the case of CS, throughout the data cycle, where training, who requests, validates, and curates the data is vital.

PROJECT SPECIFIC OBJECTIVE

SO 1
Building a pan EU Marine Citizen Science Data Network

Setup a close and actively engaged interaction with the entire network to ensure transparency to citizens, with monthly user-centric activities. The CS network will be managed using efficient technology infrastructure, data management systems, and the resulting metadata of the data such as metadata and policy matters, inspired by an open strategy to encourage its reuse and use.

SO 2
Support the development of data management standards, technologies and best practices

Support innovation of selected citizen science groups and cost-efficient technology concepts to uplift them as the data management and protocol best practices for data uptake by end users, for developing and coordinating best practices and guidelines.

SO 3
Enable and demonstrate enhanced FAIRness of the citizen science (meta)data

Demonstrate the enhanced FAIRness of the data collected by citizen science initiatives and cost-efficient technologies using the identified best practices and training, to MACH1 international data providers such as: CMCC, SMHI, Ifremer, BSRB and AODAS, and onwards to DTD, and demonstrate to the CS initiatives on citizen scientists.

CONSORTIUM

CMCC - Fondazione Centro Euro Mediterraneo per l'Avanzata Ricerca

Coordinatore del Consorzio Internazionale per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile (CIS3) e del Consorzio Internazionale per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile (CIS3)

SMHI - Statens Meteorologiska och Hydrologiska Institutet

Coordinatore del Consorzio Internazionale per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile (CIS3) e del Consorzio Internazionale per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile (CIS3)

Ifremer - Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer

Coordinatore del Consorzio Internazionale per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile (CIS3) e del Consorzio Internazionale per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile (CIS3)

SEI - European Centre for Environment and Human Health

Coordinatore del Consorzio Internazionale per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile (CIS3) e del Consorzio Internazionale per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile (CIS3)

Figure 5. Some content of the About page for CS-MACH1 project website.

4.4 Network

The Network page constitutes the operational and community heart of the CS-MACH1 website, presenting the **MCSNDN** – the core structure through which the project connects MSCIs leaders, technology developers, data-management experts, and marine researchers across Europe. The page will describe the purpose and composition of the Network Secretariat, which facilitates exchange and coordination among the various actors, ensuring the flow of knowledge, data, and best practices. Currently the Network page mainly provides information on how to join the MCSNDN through a dedicated email curated by SMHI as part of WP2, especially T2.1, inviting new initiatives, projects and target groups, to become part of the growing community (Figure 6).

An interactive directory will allow users to browse and filter organisations, initiatives, and developers by category, supporting visibility and collaboration

among members. As part of the Network, the project will be referencing and directing to:

- [EU-Citizen.Science](#) for community exchange;
- [EMODnet](#) and [SeaDataNet](#) for data ingestion and FAIR workflows;
- [SCOOP](#) for low-cost sensors and technologies;
- [CoastPredict / GlobalCoast](#) for UN-Decade synergies;
- [Ocean Best Practices System](#) for training and standardisation.

Figure 6. Some content of the Network page for CS-MACH1 project website.

4.5 Training & Guidelines

This section gathers all learning materials, guidance documents, and practical tools developed within CS-MACH1 to strengthen skills, knowledge, and data-management capacities across the marine citizen-science community. It acts as an open learning

hub, providing access to e-learning modules, video tutorials, best-practice handbooks, and FAIR-data protocols designed to support initiatives in improving data quality, interoperability, and alignment with EU and international standards. Resources will cover topics such as cost-efficient sensor deployment, metadata documentation, observation protocols, and data submission to aggregators like EMODnet and SeaDataNet. A user-friendly search and filter function allows visitors to explore materials by resource type, theme, or level of expertise, facilitating tailored access for citizen scientists, technology developers, educators, and marine researchers (Figure 7). The section also includes links to external training opportunities and partner materials, ensuring that content remains dynamic and interconnected with the broader ecosystem of open-science and ocean-literacy initiatives.

Our Training & Guidelines hub provides the wide marine citizen science data network with resources to collect, manage, and share high-quality marine data, with practical toolkits, protocols, and step-by-step tutorials for deploying cost-efficient technologies and applying FAIR data principles, to help the community elevate data quality, trust, and impact.

VIDEO **GUIDELINES** SCIENTIFIC PAPERS Q

DATA INGESTION & SHARING DATA MANAGEMENT FAIR DATA LOW-COST DEVICES DATA UPTAKE

Title	Short description	ID	Media type	Link
TITLE OF THE RESOURCE	Short description Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Vivamus at turpis vitae orci convallis ultrices.	344402942	GUIDELINES	Discover resource → = 453
TITLE OF THE RESOURCE	Short description Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Vivamus at turpis vitae orci convallis ultrices.	26345	VIDEO	Discover resource → = 453
TITLE OF THE RESOURCE	Short description Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Vivamus at turpis vitae orci convallis ultrices.	6128	VIDEO	Discover resource → = 453
TITLE OF THE RESOURCE	Short description Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Vivamus at turpis vitae orci convallis ultrices.	545245	GUIDELINES	Discover resource → = 453
TITLE OF THE RESOURCE	Short description Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Vivamus at turpis vitae orci convallis ultrices.	235214	PDF	Discover resource → = 453
TITLE OF THE RESOURCE	Short description Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Vivamus at turpis vitae orci convallis ultrices.	85787	GUIDELINES	Discover resource → = 453
TITLE OF THE RESOURCE	Short description Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Vivamus at turpis vitae orci convallis ultrices.	4324237423	VIDEO	Discover resource → = 453
TITLE OF THE RESOURCE	Short description Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Vivamus at turpis vitae orci convallis ultrices.	525252	PDF	Discover resource → = 453

Figure 7. Training & Guidelines main page layout of CS-MACH1 project website, ready to be populated.

4.6 Explore data

The Explore Data section shows how marine citizen-science data can be transformed into valuable, standardised contributions to European and global

ocean-observation systems, by first giving an overview to the main established infrastructures accepting community-gathered data such as **EMODnet**, **SeaDataNet**, and **GBIF** (Figure 8). As training and guidelines become available, this page will provide a clear explanation of the **data pathways** supported by CS-MACH1, showing how citizen-collected information can feed into these data platforms. The page will hence include guidance on dataset preparation and submission, metadata requirements, and data-quality assurance protocols, helping initiatives ensure that their data are FAIR.

From Marine Citizen Science to Global Ocean Databases

CS-MACH1 is developing the missing link between marine citizen-science observations and global ocean databases by building a [platform](#) and creating [guidelines](#) on data management, observation protocols and deployment guidance in order to:

- Support citizen science initiatives [apply observation protocols and methods](#),
- Invite initiatives to [describe their metadata and datasets](#),
- Assist [cost efficient sensor developers](#) with cloud solutions to describe their metadata and data output;
- Register all datasets as-is in [EMODnet Data Ingestion](#), where possible with direct feed.

PARTICIPATIVE DATA HUBS

Please note that the list is not exhaustive of all data hubs with current or plans to integrate marine citizen science data and it shows only key examples. From the EMODnet ingestion system, data experts will determine if datasets can feed into SeaDataNet, EuroBIS, or other hubs.

Category

All

EMODnet
The European Marine Observation and Data network is the European Program to integrate and make accessible in situ marine environmental and human activities data and data products, serving a diverse user base across various sectors.

+ More info

EXPLORE

SeaDataNet
SeaDataNet offers a robust framework for storing, standardising, and sharing oceanographic data collected by research institutes, monitoring agencies, and citizen science projects.

+ More info

EXPLORE

Figure 8. Some of the established data infrastructure showcased and linked to in the Explore Data page of CS-MACH1 project website.

4.7 Pilot Studies

The Pilot Studies section presents the **demonstration use-cases that lie at the heart of CS-MACH1’s practical implementation strategy** —located in the Northern European Seas and in the Southern European Seas. These pilots showcase how the project’s methodologies, tools, and low-cost technologies can be applied in real-world conditions to strengthen the quality, interoperability, and visibility of marine citizen-science data. Each pilot serves as **a testbed for evaluating observation protocols, FAIR-data workflows, and collaboration mechanisms between MCSI responsables, researchers, and data managers**. The section provides descriptions of the pilot cases including objectives, participating MCSIs, and key environmental parameters observed. An infographic showing the main pilot studies locations and concept was custom made to be showcased on this page and for the pilot’s communication materials (*Figure 9*). As the project progresses, the page will host more detailed descriptions, call to actions and results of the pilot studies, highlighting how citizen-generated data contribute to validated datasets and feed into EU-level infrastructures such as EMODnet.

Figure 8. Pilot Studies custom made infographic present in CS-MACH1 website Pilot Studies page.

4.8 News & Events

The News & Events section provides **ongoing updates on the activities, events and visibility of CS-MACH1**. It gathers press releases, publications, event organisation and participation announcements, and workshop reports, serving as a dynamic communication space that evolves alongside the project. Visitors can explore news

from across the consortium, learn about participation in conferences, organisation of workshops, new materials, and access calls to action or opportunities for collaboration. Once clicked on the news or event of interest, a full article page about it opens (*Figure 9*). This section ensures transparency and engagement by regularly sharing progress, highlights from the pilot projects, and outcomes from the Marine Citizen Science Data Network. Through timely updates and cross-links to social-media channels, News & Events keeps the CS-MACH1 community active, visible, and connected to the wider European citizen-science landscape.

Figure 9. News and Events page and related article page present in CS-MACH1 website.

4.9 Impact

The Impact section showcases how **CS-MACH1 goes beyond data collection and sharing, contributing to marine policy, sustainability, and the practical use of citizen-science data in European and global frameworks.** It highlights and will contain the project’s policy briefs and recommendations, co-designed with stakeholders to inform decision-making processes at EU and regional levels, and presents the Sustainability Roadmap, outlining post-project hosting and governance options for the Marine Citizen Science Data Network (*Figure 10*).

As the project progresses, this section will also illustrate how citizen-generated data and project outputs feed into key initiatives such as EDITO, the Digital Twin Ocean, and CoastPredict, bridging citizen science with advanced ocean-knowledge systems. In the coming months, the page will feature content to demonstrate how marine citizen-science observations enhance prediction, modelling, and management of

coastal and marine environments. By connecting local action with large-scale impact, this page embodies CS-MACH1’s ambition to turn citizen participation into a tangible contribution to Europe’s digital and sustainable ocean future.

Figure 10. A still from the Impact page present in CS-MACH1 website.

4.10 Deliverables

The Deliverables section provides open access to all CS-MACH1 outputs, including reports, publications, policy briefs, and communication materials. Each deliverable is open to download, listed by Work Package, submission date, leading organisation in charge and relevant published DOI, ensuring transparency and alignment with open-science principles.

No.	Deliverable name	Short description	Lead	Delivery date	Download link
D 1.2	Quality Control & Risk Management Documentation	Procedures for QC & risk plan	CMCC	Nov 2025, Nov 2026, Nov 2027	Download → a. 453
D 1.3	External Advisory Board Establishment	Formal EAB setup	CMCC	Nov 2025	Download → a. 453
D 1.4	Progress reports	Technical & admin reports, incl. KPIs	CMCC	May 2026, May 2027, Nov 2027	Download → a. 453
D 1.5	Data Management Plan (DMP)	Initial, interim & final versions	CMCC/ETT	Nov 2025, Nov 2026, Nov 2027	Download → a. 453
D 2.1	Preliminary assessment report	On data sharing needs of MCSI	VLIZ	Nov 2025	Download → a. 453
D 2.2	Final assessment report	Survey results on MCSI	VLIZ	May 2026	Download → a. 453
D 2.3	Platform selection	Identify best platform for data sharing	VLIZ	July 2026	Download → a. 453
D 3.1	State	SOTA of CS data mgmt. & sensors	MARIS	May 2026	Download → a. 453

Figure 11. A still of the deliverable table inside the Deliverable page, present in CS-MACH1 website and ready to be populated.

4.11 Contacts

The Contact section offers several ways to connect with the CS-MACH1 team and the Marine Citizen Science Data Network. It includes a general inquiry email of CMCC contacts as coordinators, social-media links, and institutional contacts of the singular partners.

5 Future Developments

The online environment and its underlying technologies continue to evolve rapidly, and the CS-MACH1 website must evolve accordingly to remain effective, accessible, and aligned with emerging digital standards. The use of flexible, cloud-based, and open-source tools within the FRAMER platform ensures that the project team — led by OutBe/SSBE under this deliverable — can continuously update, expand, and adapt the site as CS-MACH1 progresses. This approach guarantees that the website remains functional, relevant, and capable of integrating new content, visual features, and interactive modules developed in later stages of the project.

Given the early stage of this deliverable, several contents and functionalities are expected to be added and evolved as additional outputs become available through subsequent Work Packages.